

ATTITUDE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TOWARDS HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Education is the main factor of human development and as a result desirable changes are visible in human beings such as wisdom, knowledge, thinking and insight. It has the power to make an illiterate to literate and unknown to famous. Objectives of education are not related to acquiring wealth or to reach in a higher position but the true objectives of education is to make a human being to good human being. Education is continuous process which starts with the born of the child and end with death of a man. However there are different stages of education such as primary, secondary, senior secondary and higher stage with a mission to make the child civilized citizen. It is possible only when a child passes through primary to higher level.

Key Words : Attitude, Higher Education

INTRODUCTION

Higher education of any country decides the way of development and prosperity of that country. It is the quality of higher education which makes the young people analytical, practical and ideological. It is not only improving the performance of the individual but also participate in democracy. It is well known fact India is having the second highest populated country in the world after China. But a big portion of total population of India is far from the benefits of higher education. At the time of Independence only 2 lakh people were enrolled in higher education and in the year 2012 it was 1.6 crores. It reveals the fact that it is behind from other countries at international level. However India has set a target to bring the total enrollment ration about 30% of total population till 2020. According to All India Survey on education 2010 in 2010-11, 12% of undergraduate students take admission in post graduation and 1% of post graduation students take admission in Ph.D.

Higher Education

Higher education starts after Senior Secondary Education. Not only colleges and universities are included in higher education but also vocational, technical and all those institutions which are involved in providing education after Senior Secondary. The students studies different

subjects and also involves in research. It is called higher education because it is the highest level of formal education system. The system of higher education in India is very old. History reveals the fact that in ancient times India were having the organized system of higher education. Nalanda, Taxsila and Vikramshila were the famous universities of that time. These universities were so famous that people from different part of the world were enrolled to get higher education. It is also true that education passed through the Vedic age to modern age.

Higher education came into existence in modern India at that time when RajaRam Mohan Roy Hindu college in 1817 in Calcutta. At that time there were differences between Indians and Britishers regarding education and as a result Macaulay's Minute came into existence. After Macaulay's Minutes British government formed a committee named as Wood's Dispatch 1854 and it is also called Megnacarta of English education in India. The modern education of India was founded on the recommendation of this committee. After independence it was felt that some reforms were needed and particularly in the field of higher education. As a first education minister of India Maulana Azad's established UGC and his contribution in the field of education cannot be ignored. Jawaharlal Nehru, the first Prime Minister of India also emphasized on higher education as "A University of humanism, for tolerance, for reason, for the adventure of ideas and for the search for truth. It stands for the onward march of the human race toward even higher objectives. If the universities discharge their duties adequately then it will be well with the nations and the people."

'Everyone has the right to education--- and higher education shall be equally accessible to all on the basis of merit.' Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948).

Radhakrishnan Commission known as University Education Commission (1948-49) made recommendations for improving the quality of higher education and wanted higher education to be built on the foundation of Indian heritage and culture. The commission set goals for development of higher education in the country. The commission emphasized the quality of teachers and new method like tutorial system. It advocates the use of mother tongue as the medium of instruction to make learning environment more effective. It also pleaded for better admission procedure and recruitment of teachers based on merit. If once teacher was selected on the basis of merit they can make congenial environment for learning.

The Education Commission (popularly known as Kothari Commission 1964-66) report is entitled "Educational and National Development". The title of the report indicates the significance of education in national development. It recommended a clear cut educational structure (10+2+3 system) with reasonable flexibility for education for various levels. The urged the state and national level machineries to define, revise and evaluate national standards

of education. According to Commission recommendations, the major programme for qualitative improvement includes raising the economic, social and professional status of teachers. The Commission emphasized for improving the quality and scope of teachers education and in-service programme, vigorous improvement in the method of teaching and evaluation. It includes providing quality text books and other teaching materials, search for introduction of nation-wide programme of school and colleges improvement where each institute finds congenial condition to strive continually to achieve to the best results of which it is capable, and creation of 5 or 6 major universities. Above two land mark reports in fact laid down the basic frame work for the national policy for higher education in the country.

The National Policy on Education (1968) embodies that in view of sin-qua non importance of the teachers, they must be accorded and honoured place in society and their emoluments and other service conditions should be adequate and satisfactory having regard to their qualification and responsibilities, the regional language should be adopted as medium of education at the university stage and three-language formula should be accepted by all states. To make the learning more effective, the policy suggested that the quality of books should be improved, a major goal of examination reforms should be improved the reliability and validity of examination and to make evaluation a continuous process, the number of whole time students to be admitted to a college or university department should be determined with reference to the laboratory, library and other facilities and special attention should be given to the organization of post graduate courses with adequate training and research facility, games and sports should be developed in a large scale.

Prior to 1979, education was the responsibility of the States, the Central Government being concerned with certain areas like co-ordination and determination of standards in technical and higher education. A constitutional amendment passed on 1979, made education a concurrent subject being the joint responsibility of the Central and State Governments. However, no such a review was done in the next 17 years as laid down that its direction should be reviewed every five years. The then a policy was formulated at the initiative of Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi which is known as National Policy on Education 1986.

According to NPE 1986 “ Higher Education provides peoples with an opportunity to reflect on the critical, social, economic, cultural, moral and spiritual issues facing humanity. It contributes to National Development through dissemination of specialized knowledge and skills. It is therefore, a crucial factor for survival. Being at the apex of educational pyramid, it has also a key role in producing teachers for the educational system.”

Need of the Study

The Indian system of higher education is one of the largest systems of the world. In 1950-51 India were having 30 universities and 695 colleges but in 2012-13 India were having 700 universities and 35000 colleges. It is also fact that with the passage of time Gross Enrollment Ratio improved. In 1950-51 GER were 0.21 million and in 2011-12 it was 22 million. In terms of percentage of total population GER was 19.46 in 2013-14. It discloses that 80.54% of the total population was far away from higher education.

The State Bihar was the centre of Higher Education in ancient period. Bihar was the land where Nalanda and Vikramshila University belongs and known at International level. But at the time of British government Bihar was behind other state in higher education. In 19th century, Bengal were having 44 colleges but on the other hand Bihar were having only 5 colleges. In 1862, Patna college, in 1887 Tej Narayan Jubilee college, in 1889 National college Bihar and in 1897 Dimond Jubilee college Munger were established. It was need of the hour after partition of Bihar, Bengal and Orissa to establish a University in Bihar and as a result Patna University was established in 1917. After independence the position of Bihar was not satisfactory in terms of the development in higher education. In 1952 a separate University was established and called Bihar University was the offshoot of Patna University. Three Universities namely Bihar University, Ranchi University and Bhagalpur University were the offshoot of Bihar University by Bihar State Universities Act 1960. The proportion of universities were less than the growth of population and as a result the level of higher education decreased. Bihar is the least literate state in India but having the third position in terms of population. According to 2011 census the literacy rate of Bihar was 63.8%. Annual status of higher education of States and Union Territories of India 2013 reveals that the GER of Bihar was 10.5% , but it was 19.4% at National Level. Thus the researcher feels that a study should be conducted to know the attitude of students towards higher education.

Statement of the Problem

Present study states “*Attitude of secondary school students towards higher education*”.

.Objectives of the Study

Following are the objectives of the study:

1. To know the difference between the attitude of boys and girls students towards higher education.
2. To know the difference between the attitude of urban and rural students towards higher education.
3. To find out the difference between the attitude of urban boys and rural boys students towards higher education.

4. To find out the difference between the attitude of urban girls and rural girls students towards higher education.

Hypotheses of the Study

Following are the hypotheses of the study:

1. There is no significance difference between the attitude of boys and girls students towards higher education.
2. There is no significance difference between the attitude of urban boys and girls students towards higher education.
3. There is no significance difference between the attitude of urban and rural boys students towards higher education.
4. There is no significance difference between the attitude of urban girls and rural boys students towards higher education.

Delimitation

The present study is delimited in terms of area, content and sample as follows:

- The study was confined to the Sitamarhi District of Bihar State.
- The sample included students from secondary school only.
- A sample of only 50 girls and 50 boys students taken from 4 school of Sitamarhi District of Bihar State, which cannot present the whole population. So, the present research can be generalized keeping in view the limitations.
- In spite of all precautions that have been taken for collections of data few respondents would have not been that sincere and honest as they should have been.

METHODOLOGY

Population and Sample

The population for the present study comprised of all the schools of Sitamarhi district and all the students of these school. And then as per the objectives of the study, a list of school of Sitamarhi Districts of Bihar was obtained from website. Firstly, four school and then 50 boys students & 50 girls students were selected on the stratified random sampling.. Thus, sample for the present study comprised of 100 students studying in 9th and 10th from these school of Sitamarhi district.

Tools of the Study

The tools used in the present investigation are listed below:

A questionnaire was constructed and standardized by the investigator with the help of the expert and used in the present investigation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Attitude of Boys and Girls Students towards Higher Education

To know the difference between the attitude of boys and girls students towards higher education the scale was administered to 50 boys and 50 girls' students. Table 4.1 below shows mean and standard deviation attained on questionnaire. Analysis of **Attitude of Boys and Girls Students towards Higher Education** has been done below:

Table 4.1 Attitude of Boys and Girls Students towards Higher Education

Variable	Number	Mean	SD	t-value	Result	Hypothesis
Boys	50	47.94	7.192	0.7233	Not Significant	Accepted
Girls	50	47.44	6.887			

Table 4.1 reveals that the mean score of boys and girls are 47.94 & 47.44 respectively with a t-value of 0.7233 which is not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level. It means that there is no significance difference between the attitude of boys and girls students towards higher education and Ho-1 is accepted.

Attitude of Urban and Rural Students towards Higher Education

To know the difference between the attitude of urban and rural students towards higher education the investigator administered the questionnaire on total students which includes Urban and Rural students and analysis is done below:

Table 4.2 Attitude of Urban and Rural Students towards Higher Education

Variable	Number	Mean	SD	t-value	Result	Hypothesis
Urban Students	50	47.38	6.366	0.6606	Not Significant	Accepted
Rural Students	50	48	7.653			

Table 4.2 disclose that the mean score of urban and rural students are 47.38 & 48 respectively with a t-value of 0.6606 which is not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level. It shows that there is no significance difference between the attitude of urban and rural students towards higher education and Ho-2 is accepted.

Attitude of Urban and Rural Boys Students towards Higher Education

To find out the difference between the attitude of urban boys and rural boys students towards higher education the questionnaire was administered on 25 rural boys and 25 urban students and interpretation is as follows:

Table 4.3 Attitude of Urban and Rural Boys Students towards Higher Education

Variable	Number	Mean	SD	t-value	Result	Hypothesis
Rural Boys	25	49.32	6.694	0.1774	Not Significant	Accepted
Urban Boys	25	46.56	7.539			

From table 4.3 it can interpret that the mean score of rural and urban boys are 49.32 & 46.56 respectively with a t-value of 0.1774 which is not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level. It can be safely conclude that there is no significance difference between the attitude of urban and rural boys towards higher education, so Ho-3 is accepted.

Attitude of Urban Girls and Rural Girls Students towards Higher Education

To find out the difference between the attitude of urban girls and rural girls students towards higher education the same questionnaire have been used and analysis is as follows: **Table 4.4**

Attitude of Urban Girls and Rural Girls Students towards Higher Education

Variable	Number	Mean	SD	t-value	Result	Hypothesis
Rural Girls	25	48.88	8.434	0.440	Not Significant	Accepted
Urban Girls	25	48.20	4.949			

From above table 4.4 it can be analyse that the mean score of rural girls and urban girls are 48.88 & 48.20 respectively with a t-value of 0.440 which is not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 level. It can be conclude that there is no significance difference between the attitude of urban and rural boys towards higher education, so Ho-4 is accepted.

CONCLUSIONS

Bihar is the lowest literate state of India. It is visible from the above fact that the students were having the positive attitude towards higher education. The facilities which are provided by the government are inadequate. More universities and colleges should be open for higher learning. Now time has come to talk about universalities of higher education. However it was found that there is no significance difference between the attitude of boys and girls students, urban and rural students but the means of boys is better than the girls. Thus it is the duty of the democratic government to plan and invest for the betterment of higher education to make human capital more empower and ultimately prosperity, development and humanity will be the result.

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